

ISic0370

I.Sicily inscription 0370

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR141185

1. [D (is)] M (anibus) s (acrum)
2. [---]ntelus Seleucus
3. [---] ann (is) XIII m (ensibus) VIII P (ublius)
4. [---]ntelus Seleucus pat (er)
5. [---]pio et Simbolico
6. [---ne]poti eius vix (it) ann (is) XVI
7. [---] m (ensibus) VII.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491581

EDR 141185

EDCS 21900410

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7088 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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